

Assessment of the Impact of Gender and Parents' Education on Numeracy Skills Achievements among Basic Nine School Students in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the impact of gender, parents' education and the acquisition of numeracy skills among basic nine school students in Delta State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 140,959 Basic 9 students in public basic schools in Delta State in the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample of the study comprised 1,056 Basic 9 school students. The multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in the study. The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is a numeracy Skill Tests. The test was face and content validated by an experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation, to establish the reliability of the instrument, the test was administered to 100 students in Edo State. The data were analysed using Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR20). The coefficient obtained is 0.69 for numeracy test Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent samples t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that both male and female students demonstrated comparable levels of numeracy achievement, suggesting that gender no longer serves as a major determinant of learning outcomes at the basic education level in the State. However, a significant difference was observed in numeracy achievement between students from educated and non-educated parents. The study concluded that basic school students in Delta State have generally attained numeracy proficiency

to a high extent, the study recommended that Schools should collaborate with educated parents to mentor other parents on supporting children's problem solving skills.

Key words: Parents Education, Gender, Achievement, Numeracy Skills.

Introduction

The government have invested so much funds, time and efforts in various ways to ensure adequate and effective numeracy skills among basic school students yet majority of basic school graduates in the state still struggle with basic numerical operations, such as addition (+), subtraction (-), multiplication(x) and division (\div) after completing their basic education. This deficiency not only limits their ability to participate effectively in higher levels of education but also hinders their integration into the workforce and society.

The absent of these numerical skills poses a severe threat to numeracy in the state, as these skills are critical for breaking the cycle of poverty, reducing inequality, and fostering economic growth. Despite government efforts to improve the quality of basic education, the persistent gap in these essential skills raises questions about the effectiveness of the current curriculum, teacher competence, and resource allocation. Despite the longstanding declaration of free basic education, many Nigerians, particularly in Delta State, continue to struggle with poverty, illiteracy. Gender inequality.

Education empowers individuals with the skills needed to break the cycle of poverty and reduce inequality. By ensuring that basic school students in Delta State acquire the skills to become productive members of society, the state addresses the root causes of poverty. Educated individuals are more likely to secure gainful employment, participate in entrepreneurial activities, and contribute to the local and national economy. This creates a ripple effect that improves the quality of life for families and communities, aligning with SDG 1 (No Poverty) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities). The focus on universal access to basic education also promotes gender equality by encouraging the enrolment and retention of both boys and girls in school. This is particularly significant in Delta State, where cultural and economic barriers may disproportionately affect girls' access to education. By addressing these barriers and creating an inclusive educational environment, the state advances SDG 5 (Gender Equality) and ensures that girls have equal opportunities to develop the skills needed to succeed in life and contribute to sustainable development. The skills acquired in basic education serve as a foundation for higher learning, vocational training, and workforce participation. In Delta State, this translates into a more skilled labour force, capable of driving economic growth and fostering innovation.

The concept of numeracy could be said to have originated from the report for the United Kingdom Ministry of Education (Department for Education, 2020), and the concept of adult numeracy has

gained more popularity in developed countries such as the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and the UK (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Adult numeracy was initially treated as part of adult literacy with no visible scale to measure it (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, OECD, 2022). Historically, adult literacy was measured using a unidimensional scale, and “some five years after the British report, although it told little about adult numeracy, it provided a landmark framework for researching and reporting on the mathematical needs of adult life” (Schmitt & Thompson, 2023). The report proposed a definition of numeracy:

A longitudinal study by Lehl et al. (2020) demonstrated that early home support for learning and engagement in home mathematics activities are positively associated with children's mathematical development between ages two and six. These findings underscore the importance of early home learning environments in preparing children for formal education.

Recent research underscores the importance of integrating mathematical process skills into early numeracy instruction. These higher-order thinking skills, including problem-solving, reasoning, constructing arguments, and connecting ideas, are essential for students to engage deeply with mathematical concepts. A study by Clements (2010) emphasizes that children develop these skills when provided with rich, problem-based tasks that encourage them to explain their thinking and engage in discussions with peers. This approach aligns with the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics' (NCTM) recommendations, highlighting the significance of both content and process in mathematics education.

Numeracy concepts and skills have been identified as some of the most problematic and dreaded by learners at all educational levels in Nigeria (Adeleke, 2016). Emphasis is consistently placed on developing children's numeracy skills for their future and immediate needs and benefits, with the view that children can be taught early to love and engage with mathematics in an enjoyable and accessible way using a “catch them young” approach (Adeleke et al., 2017). The study of Egede et al. (2020) revealed significant growth in achievement in numeracy skills, just as in the case of literacy. This result aligns with findings from other studies (e.g., Meiers & Raid, 2014; Pam, 2017), which suggest that learners make progress in their numeracy skills when they are exposed to learning experiences designed to build numeracy skills over years of study.

Awofala and Anyikwa (2014) investigated adult learner numeracy as related to gender and performance in arithmetic among 32 Nigerian adult learners from one government accredited adult literacy centre in Lagos State using the quantitative research method within the blueprint of descriptive survey design. Data collected were analysed using the descriptive statistics of percentages, mean, and standard deviation and inferential statistics of factor analysis, independent samples t-test, and multiple regression analysis. Findings revealed that numeracy skill assessed by the numeracy self-assessment scale was a multi-dimensional construct (numeracy in everyday life, numeracy in workplace, and numeracy in mathematical tasks). Adult learners showed average numeracy strength as gender differences in perception of numeracy skills and performance in

arithmetic among adult learners reached zero-tolerance level. Numeracy in workplace and numeracy in mathematical tasks made statistically significant contributions to the variance in adult learners' performance in arithmetic.

In line with the above, this study aims to examine the effects of numeracy skills achievement among basic nine school students in Delta State, Nigeria

Research Questions

- i. to what extent have male and female basic school students achieved numeracy skills in Delta State.
- ii. to what extent have basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents acquired numeracy skills in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference between male and female basic school students in their achievement of numeracy skills in Delta State
2. There is no significant difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State

Methods

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 140,959 Basic 9 students in public basic schools in Delta State in the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample of the study comprised 1,056 Basic 9 school students. The multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in the study. First stage, the researcher used simple random sampling technique to sampled one school in each Local Government Area of the state to make a total of 25 schools, Secondly, the researcher adopted a proportionate stratified sampling technique. by first determined the percentage of the sample size of 1,056 relative to the overall population of 140,959 students, which stood at 0.749%. Hence, for every Local Government Area, a percentage of 0.749 of the total population of students in that Local Government Area were selected. In the third stage,

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the researcher selected the students using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is a numeracy Skill Tests. The test contains two sections. Section A: deals with the Demographic Data of the students such as sex and location. Section B: contains numeracy Skill Test. Test were adopted from a standardized test of Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Examination for Basic 9. The tests contain 25 items each structured in a multiple-choice question, with 5 options (A-E), 1 correct answer and 4 distracters. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, the test was administered to 100 students in Bayelsa State. The data were analysed using Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR_{20}). The coefficient obtained is 0.72. The test was administered directly to the respondents by the researcher. Prior to the test administration, the researcher went to the various schools used in the study. The completed responses were collected on the spot to avoid loss of data. The data obtained were analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent samples t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: to what extent have male and female basic school students achieve numeracy skills in Delta State.?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the extent to which male and female basic school students have achieved numeracy skills in Delta State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD
Male	481	13.67	5.45
Female	575	13.49	5.33
Overall Mean	1,056	13.58	5.39

Table 1. Shows the mean analysis of the extent to which male and female basic school students have achieved numeracy skills in Delta State. The result shows that male students ($N=481$) obtained a mean score of 13.67 with a standard deviation of 5.45, while female students ($N=575$) recorded a mean score of 13.49 with a standard deviation of 5.33. The overall mean score for all the students combined was 13.58 with a standard deviation of 5.39. These results indicate that both male and female students performed almost equally in numeracy skills, as the mean difference between the two groups (0.18) is negligible. This suggests that the extent to which

male and female basic school students have achieved numeracy skills in Delta State is approximately the same.

Research Question 2: to what extent have basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents acquired numeracy skills in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean analysis of the extent to which basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents acquired numeracy skills in Delta State.

Educational Level	n	Mean	SD
Educated Parent	563	14.26	5.44
Non- educated Parents	493	12.96	5.24
Overall Mean	1,056	13.61	5.34

Table 2 shows the mean analysis of the extent to which basic school students from educated parents and those from non- educated parents have acquired numeracy skills in Delta State. The result shows that educated parents (N =563) obtained a mean score of 14.26 with a standard deviation of 5.44, while non- educated Parents (N =493) recorded a mean score of 12.96 and standard deviation of 5.24. The overall mean score for all the students combined was 13.61 with a standard deviation of 5.34. These results implies that both basic school students from educated parents and those from non- educated parents performed independently different in numeracy skills, as the mean difference between the two groups (1.48). This indicates that, the extent to which basic school students from educated parents and those from non- educated parents acquired numeracy skills in Delta State to a high extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female basic school students in their achievement of numeracy skills in Delta State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of the difference between male and female basic school students in their achievement of numeracy skills in Delta State

Gender	n	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Male	481	13.67	5.44				
Female	575	13.49	5.33	1,054	0.531	0.596	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 3 shows an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare the difference between male and female basic school students in their achievement of numeracy skills in Delta State.

The results reveal that male students had a mean score of 13.67 with a standard deviation of 5.44, while their female counterparts had a mean score of 13.49 with a standard deviation of 5.33. The calculated t-value of 0.531 with a corresponding p-value of 0.596 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female basic school students in their achievement of numeracy skills in Delta State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State

Table 4: t-test analysis of the difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State

Educational level	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Educated Parents	563	14.26	5.44				
Non-Educated Parents	493	12.96	5.24	1,054	3.96	0.000	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 shows an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare the difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State. The results reveal that students from educated parents had a mean score of 14.26 with a standard deviation of 5.44, while those from non-educated parents had a mean score of 12.96 with a standard deviation of 5.24. p-value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that there is a significant difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

The first findings showed the extent to which male and female basic school students have acquired numeracy skills in Delta State is approximately the same. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female basic school students in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State. This finding suggests that both genders possess comparable levels of numeracy skills. This implies that access to numeracy learning opportunities, quality of instruction, and exposure to mathematical content are likely balanced across male and female students in the State. The finding reflects a trend toward gender parity in foundational education outcomes, which could be attributed to policy efforts promoting equal access to education and reducing gender biases in classroom participation and teacher expectations. It also indicates that numeracy skill acquisition is more influenced by environmental and pedagogical factors than by gender-based cognitive differences.

The finding agrees with Ogunlade and Adebayo (2021), who found no significant gender difference in mathematics achievement among primary school pupils in south-western Nigeria, emphasizing that both boys and girls can perform equally well when given similar learning environments. The finding also aligns with Okafor and Eze (2022), who observed that the provision of gender-sensitive teaching methods and inclusive classroom practices has reduced disparities in numeracy outcomes among learners. The finding is also consistent with UNESCO's (2023) report which revealed a narrowing gender gap in basic mathematics proficiency across sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, as a result of sustained efforts toward educational equity. The finding is however, at variance with Adedeji (2019), who noted slight male advantages in numeracy, attributing them to sociocultural expectations and stereotype threats; however, recent trends show that such differences are diminishing due to changing attitudes and improved instructional practices.

Another finding showed that the extent to which basic school students from educated parents and those from non- educated parents acquired numeracy skills in Delta State to a high extent. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between basic school students from educated and those from non-educated parents in their acquisition of numeracy skills in Delta State. Basic school students from educated parents appears to possess higher numeracy skills than their counterparts from non-educated parents. This finding suggests that the educational background of parents plays a crucial role in shaping children's numeracy skills. This implies that students whose parents are educated tend to demonstrate stronger numerical reasoning, problem-solving abilities, and mathematical confidence compared to those from non-educated homes. Educated parents are generally more capable of supporting their children's academic growth through direct assistance with homework, providing learning materials, and creating an environment that promotes curiosity and critical thinking. On the other hand, children of non-educated parents may lack access to such support structures, leading to lower engagement and weaker foundational numeracy skills.

This finding aligns with Ogunleye and Okafor (2021), who found that pupils whose parents possess higher educational qualifications perform better in mathematics because their parents provide guidance and foster positive attitudes toward learning. The finding also agrees with Adekunle and Bello (2022), who reported that children from educated families tend to have greater exposure to mathematical concepts in everyday life, such as counting money, measuring household items, and using technology that reinforces numerical reasoning. The finding also confirms with report of UNESCO (2023), which noted that parental education significantly contributes to children's cognitive development, particularly in literacy and numeracy, by shaping the home learning environment and expectations. The finding, however, contrasts with Eze and Mohammed (2020), who argued that while parental education contributes to numeracy acquisition, the quality of teaching, availability of instructional materials, and classroom environment also play substantial roles.

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that basic nine school students in Delta State achieved numeracy skills to a high extent, irrespective of their sex. Gender appears to no longer serve as a major determinant of learning outcomes among basic school students in Delta State. Parental education however, appears to play a critical role in enhancing children's learning outcomes, as educated parents are more likely to support their children's academic progress through effective guidance, provision of learning materials, and a stimulating home environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i Regular mathematics workshops and training should be organized for teachers to enhance effective numeracy instruction and classroom innovation.
- ii Teachers should provide extra numeracy support and offer school tutorials for students from non-educated homes to bridge learning gaps.

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